

Analysis of ciguatoxins in fish with a single-step sandwich immunoassay

Jaume Reverté^{a,b}, Shivangi Shukla^a, Takeshi Tsumuraya^c, Masahiro Hiram^c,
Jean Turquet^d, Jorge Diogène^a, Mònica Campàs^{a,*}

^a IRTA, Marine and Continental Waters (AMiC), 43540 La Ràpita, Catalonia, Spain

^b Universitat Rovira i Virgili, C/ St. Llorenç 21, 43201 Reus, Spain

^c Department of Biological Sciences, Graduate School of Science, Osaka Metropolitan University, 599-8570 Osaka, Japan

^d CITEB, C/o CYROI, 2 Rue Maxime Rivière, 97490 Sainte Clotilde, La Réunion, France

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ABSTRACT

Ciguatoxins (CTXs) are the primary cause of ciguatera poisoning (CP), one of the most prevalent non-bacterial seafood-borne illnesses worldwide. With no cure available beyond palliative treatments to alleviate symptoms, effective CP management relies on prevention. However, the detection of CTXs in seafood poses significant analytical challenges due to their typically low concentrations in specimens and the high variability among CTX congeners, many of which remain poorly characterized. These challenges have led to a growing demand for the development of rapid, sensitive, and user-friendly bioanalytical tools for CP surveillance. In this study, several simplified sandwich immunoassay strategies were evaluated for the detection of Pacific CTXs in fish. Among them, the single-step strategy was identified as the most promising, as it enables the detection of Pacific CTXs in complex fish matrixes within only 40 min at levels as low as 0.01 µg CTX1B equivalents/kg of fish, aligned with the safety guidance level proposed by the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Unlike traditional sandwich immunoassays, which require several sequential incubation steps, the single-step strategy involves a simultaneous incubation of all components with the sample, uniquely followed by a washing and substrate incubation step prior to signal measurement. This approach significantly reduces both the complexity and time required for analysis, positioning this immunoassay as a highly promising tool for CP risk assessment and management.

1. Introduction

Ciguatera poisoning (CP) is a widespread seafood-related illness caused by the consumption of fish or other marine organisms contaminated with ciguatoxins (CTXs) (Loeffler et al., 2021). The origin of these highly toxic compounds with a characteristic polycyclic polyether structure is attributed to some dinoflagellate species of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* (Chinain et al., 2010; Wang et al., 2022), which are known to produce CTXs and potential CTX-precursor molecules as products of their secondary metabolism. Several CTX congeners are present at different trophic levels as a consequence of bioaccumulation and biotransformation processes in marine animals (Clausing et al., 2024; Ikehara et al., 2017). In fact, CTXs and their precursors enter the marine food webs through benthic-feeding organisms (mainly herbivore fishes) to be subsequently transferred to top-predator organisms (carnivore fishes), following a complex biomagnification process that, ultimately, may reach humans and cause CP

(Lehane and Lewis, 2000). Historically, CP has been considered endemic to tropical and subtropical regions, where the incidence is estimated to be up to 500,000 cases per year, or even more due to unreported cases in remote areas and the difficulties in diagnosis (Friedman et al., 2017). However, during the last decades, CP has emerged in new places, particularly in Europe (Canals et al., 2021), where it may pose a serious food safety threat and a public health concern if proper control measures are not implemented (Reverté et al., 2023).

The biological target of CTXs are the voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSCs), a cell membrane protein involved in the initiation and propagation of action potentials in neuronal and other excitable tissues (Catterall, 2012). The activation of VGSCs by CTXs leads to clinical manifestations that combine several gastrointestinal (e.g. vomiting, diarrhoea, nausea), neurological (e.g. tingling, itching) and cardiovascular (e.g. hypotension, bradycardia) symptoms (Gaiani et al., 2023). The severity of these symptoms is highly variable and depends on the quantity of fish ingested and its CTX profile (Nicholson and Lewis,

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: monica.campas@irta.cat (M. Campàs).

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2006). To date, >30 CTX congeners have been described. Initially, they had been classified into three groups according to their geographical origin: Pacific, Caribbean or Indian CTXs (Nicholson and Lewis, 2006). Although this classification is still in use, it must be highlighted that the presence of the different CTX congeners in fish is not restricted to specific geographical areas and, for example, Pacific CTXs (initially isolated from Pacific fishes) have also been detected in fishes from the Indian Ocean (Leonardo et al., 2020). Therefore, CTXs have been recently re-classified into CTX4A group, CTX3C group, Caribbean CTXs group and Indian CTXs group by Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and World Health Organization (WHO) experts (FAO and WHO, 2020). The toxicity of the different CTX congeners depends on their affinity against the target. Among the different CTXs, CTX1B (also known as P-CTX-1) is considered one of the most toxic congeners, presenting an acute intraperitoneal median lethal dose (LD₅₀) of 0.25 µg/kg in mice (Lewis et al., 1991). However, it is important to note that the absorption of CTX1B may vary depending on the route of administration, with oral administration requiring more time to reach peak blood levels compared to intraperitoneal administration (Dechraoui Bottein et al., 2011). In general terms, the toxic effects of CTXs abate after a few days or weeks, in the most severe cases, they can persist for months or years. Additionally, rapid deaths due to organic or systemic failures after the consumption of fish contaminated with CTXs, although rare, have also been described (Diogène et al., 2017; Hamilton et al., 2010). Since CP has no cure other than palliative treatments to relieve the symptoms and given the potential threat that CP can pose to human health, CP prevention through the rapid detection of CTXs in fish is crucial.

Fish containing CTX levels exceeding 0.1 µg CTX1B equivalents (equiv.)/kg have been shown to induce initial mild CP clinical manifestations (Lehane and Lewis, 2000). Assuming a fish consumption of 500 g per meal, a human body weight of 50 kg and an uncertainty factor of 10 (for intraspecies differences) (FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations) 2004), the United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) has proposed a safety guidance level of 0.01 µg CTX1B equiv./kg of fish, not legally enforceable (Chinain et al., 2021). However, other works point out that the minimum dose to cause illness by oral intake could be higher than the one considered for the calculation of the FDA safety guidance level (Yashumoto, 2005). Therefore, this level could change in future re-evaluations as more CP data is compiled. In Europe, fishery products containing CTXs cannot be marketed, but neither regulatory limits nor detection techniques have been set (REGULATION (EC) 2024). The European Food Safety Authority (EFSA) has adopted the FDA safety guidance level (EFSA Panel on contaminants in the food chain, 2010), but concrete specifications regarding the analytical methodology to use for the detection of CTXs in fish are still lacking. This situation has fostered the development of several analytical techniques for the detection of CTXs.

Historically, the mouse bioassay (MBA) has been one of the most important methods for the toxicological characterisation of toxic compounds, including CTXs (Reverté et al., 2023). However, its use has been banned in many countries due to the ethical concerns derived from the use of live animals, the lack of specificity and the inter-assay variability (Reverté et al., 2023). Cell-based assays (CBAs) are an interesting alternative to MBA for the characterisation of toxic compounds using established cell models instead of live animals. In this case, the measurement of the toxicity of a compound is based on the assessment of morphological or viability changes in cultured cells after being exposed to toxins or contaminated fish samples (Kogure et al., 1988; Manger et al., 1993; Manger et al., 1995). Generally, the cellular models used with CBA (e.g., Neuro-2a cells) perform well and are adopted regularly as screening toxicological tools, but require sensitisation pretreatments with auxiliary drugs (e.g., veratridine and ouabain) for appropriate detection of CTXs. This requirement increases the analysis costs and, as small changes in veratridine/ouabain can affect the performance of the assay, changes in CBA sensitivity may occur (subsequently increasing the analysis variability). Additionally, CBA usually requires >48 h to get

a result. Some other analytical techniques developed for the detection of CTXs in fish, such as liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) (Oshiro et al., 2021) or receptor binding assays (RBAs) (Díaz-Asencio et al., 2024), require highly sophisticated instrumentation and/or specialised personnel for experimental handling and data interpretation. Considering all these limitations, there is an increasing need for the development of rapid and user-friendly analytical tools able to detect CTXs at the FDA safety guidance level and to ensure appropriate seafood management and CP surveillance. Immunoassays may represent a solution to this necessity.

The development of immunoassays for the detection of CTXs has been limited for many years due to the structural complexity of these toxins and the scarce availability of CTX standards, which hampered the production of antibodies (Abs). In a first stage, Hokama and coworkers produced several polyclonal (pAb) and monoclonal (mAb) Abs against CTX, which were applied in the development of several immunoassays and strip tests for the detection of CTXs in fish (Hokama et al., 1977; Hokama, 1985; Hokama et al., 1987; Hokama et al., 1998; Park, 1995). However, the lack of information about which type of CTXs these antibodies were able to detect or the possibility to induce false positive/negative results as a consequence of undesired cross-reactivities with other marine toxins compromised their applicability (Bienfang et al., 2011; Ebesu and Campora, 2012; Dickey et al., 1994). It was not until later, with the introduction of synthetic haptens mimicking the ends of different Pacific CTX congeners, that the production of highly specific mAbs with no cross-reactivity with other marine toxins was successfully achieved (Nagumo et al., 2004; Oguri et al., 2003; Tsumuraya et al., 2010; Tsumuraya et al., 2014; Tsumuraya et al., 2006; Tsumuraya et al., 2018; Tsumuraya et al., 2012). These mAbs have been used in the development of a magnetic bead (MB)-based sandwich immunoassay (Leonardo et al., 2020; Gaiani et al., 2020), which has served as the biorecognition principle of several biosensing tools for Pacific CTXs (Leonardo et al., 2020; Gaiani et al., 2020; Campàs et al., 2022). In this immunoassay, two capture mAbs (3G8 and 10C9) are immobilised on MBs, resulting in two different conjugates: the 3G8-MB conjugate, which is specific against Pacific CTXs from the CTX1B series, and the 10C9-MB conjugate, which is specific against Pacific CTXs from the CTX3C series. These mAb-MB conjugates are generally used together (Leonardo et al., 2020), to get a composite response providing the amount of Pacific CTXs from the CTX1B and CTX3C series present in a sample. However, they can also be used separately (Gaiani et al., 2020), if discrimination between Pacific CTXs of the CTX1B and CTX3C series is pursued. After exposing the mAb-MB conjugates to the sample for capturing the Pacific CTXs, a reporter mAb (8H4), able to detect both CTX1B and CTX3C congeners, is added to the system. This reporter mAb is modified with biotin, which interacts with an enzyme label (polyHRP-streptavidin) that produces a measurable signal proportional to the amount of Pacific CTXs present in the sample.

Even though this MB-based immunoassay presents a high sensitivity, it requires several incubation and washing steps, which may hamper its applicability as a rapid test by non-skilled end-users and/or in low-resource settings. Therefore, in this work, we propose four simplified protocols based on the previously developed MB-based sandwich immunoassay with the aim of providing a rapid, easy-to-use and highly sensitive tool for the detection of Pacific CTXs in fish. The performance of these immunoassays has been carefully evaluated and all the optimisation and validation steps have been rationally designed and discussed. Additionally, this work provides several key concepts that can be applied in the design and development of other sandwich immunoassays to provide simplified strategies for the detection of target analytes at trace concentrations in complex matrixes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Reagents and solutions

Dynabeads M-270 Carboxylic Acid, containing 2×10^9 beads/mL, were obtained from Invitrogen (Life Technologies, S.A., Alcobendas, Spain). Potassium phosphate monobasic, potassium phosphate dibasic, Tween-20, bovine serum albumin (BSA), 4-morpholineethanesulfonic acid (MES) hydrate, N-(3-(dimethylaminopropyl)-N'-ethylcarbodiimide hydrochloride (EDC), N-hydroxysuccinimide (NHS) and 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) liquid substrate were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Tres Cantos, Spain). Mili-Q water (Millipore, Bedford, USA) was used to prepare all buffers and solutions. PolyHRP-streptavidin, at 0.5 mg/mL, was obtained from Thermo Fisher (Barcelona, Spain). Acetone and diethyl ether were obtained from Chem-Lab (Zedelgem, Belgium), and ethanol, methanol and *n*-hexane were obtained from Honeywell (Barcelona, Spain). CTX1B standard was obtained from Prof. Richard J. Lewis (The Queensland University, Australia). The 3G8, 10C9 and 8H4 mAbs had been prepared by immunising mice with keyhole limpet hemocyanine (KLH) conjugates of rationally designed synthetic haptens (Nagumo et al., 2004; Oguri et al., 2003; Tsumuraya et al., 2010; Tsumuraya et al., 2014; Tsumuraya et al., 2006; Tsumuraya et al., 2018; Tsumuraya et al., 2012). The 8H4 mAb was biotinylated with the EZ-Link™ NHS-PEG4 Biotinylation Kit from Thermo Fisher (Barcelona, Spain), following the manufacturer's instructions. Unreacted biotin labels were removed using the Zeba Spin Desalting Columns (7 kDa MWCO, 2 mL), included in the kit.

2.2. Equipment

Magnetic separation was performed using a MagneSphere Technology Magnetic Separation Stand (for 12 0.5-mL tubes) and a PolyAtract System 1000 Magnetic Separation Stand (for one 15-mL tube) from Promega Corporation (Madison, WI, USA). Colorimetric measurements were performed with a Synergy LX microplate reader from BioTek (Agilent Technologies, Inc., Santa Clara, CA, USA).

2.3. Fish samples and toxin extraction

The fish used in this work were collected from various locations in the Indian Ocean (La Réunion (RE) and Mauritius). A preliminary screening of the catches at the dockside was conducted in accordance with local regulations, which designate certain species as potentially toxic. Species identification was confirmed by experts through morphological assessment following FAO guides (Heemstra and Randall, 1993; Allen, 1985), FishBase (FishBase, 2025a; FishBase, 2025b) and the specific guide on coastal fishes of the Western Indian Ocean from the South African Institute for Aquatic Biodiversity (Heemstra et al., 2022), once the selected fishes arrived at laboratory facilities. *Variola louti*, commonly known as the yellow-edged lyretail, has an elongated body with a distinctive lyre-shaped caudal fin, a reddish to purplish body covered in small blue spots, and a yellow margin on its fins. In contrast, *Lutjanus bohar*, or the two-spot red snapper, has a more robust body with a uniformly red to reddish-brown coloration and a characteristic dark spot at the base of the pectoral fin, sometimes accompanied by a second spot on the upper flank (Heemstra and Randall, 1993; Allen, 1985; FishBase, 2025a; FishBase, 2025b; Heemstra et al., 2022). One *V. louti* flesh extract, obtained from a pool of different specimens that tested negative with CBA and the original immunoassay (strategy A), was used in the spiking experiments. Four naturally contaminated fishes of the species *V. louti* and *L. bohar* were analysed (Table 1). Fish extracts were freshly prepared for this work, as previously described (Diogène et al., 2017). Briefly, 10 g of fish flesh was weighed in a tube and heated on a water bath set at 70 °C for 15 min. Subsequently, 20 mL of acetone was added, and the sample was homogenised for 2 min with an Ultra-turrax blender at full speed. Then, the tube was centrifuged at 3000 × g

Table 1

Sampling data of the naturally contaminated fishes used in this work.

Fish species	Sample	Location	Sampling date	Weight (kg)
<i>Variola louti</i>	04/DIV/03	Mount La Pérouse (RE)	April 2004	6.1
	15/41	Mauritius	March 2015	6.0
<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>	03/DIV/21	Mount La Pérouse (RE)	January 2002	7.0
	02/DIV/38	Mount La Pérouse (RE)	August 2003	6.0

for 10 min at 20 °C to obtain the supernatant. A second extraction with an additional 20 mL of acetone was performed. Both supernatants were pooled and filtered through 0.45 µm nylon filters. The extract was dried, reconstituted with 5 mL of a methanol/water solution (9:1 (v/v)) and partitioned twice with 5 mL of *n*-hexane. The *n*-hexane phases were discarded, and the resulting aqueous methanol phases were pooled, dried and reconstituted with 5 mL of an ethanol/water solution (1:3 (v/v)). The extract was then partitioned twice with 5 mL of diethyl ether. The diethyl ether fractions were collected, pooled and dried, and the residue was finally resuspended in 4 mL of methanol. The resulting extracts, containing flesh at 2500 mg/mL, were kept at -20 °C until required. For the spiking experiments, 2 mL of the *V. louti* negative flesh extract was mixed with 50 µL of a CTX1B standard solution at 1000 pg/mL (both in methanol). The spiked extract was then dried and reconstituted in 2 mL of assay buffer, resulting in a final concentration of 25 pg CTX1B/mL or, given that the extract contained 2500 mg/mL of flesh tissue, of 0.01 µg CTX1B/kg fish (which is the FDA safety guidance level for CTXs (Chinain et al., 2021)).

2.4. Original and simplified immunoassay strategies

The simplified strategies proposed in this work were based on a previously developed MB-based sandwich immunoassay for the detection of Pacific CTXs of the CTX1B and CTX3C series (Leonardo et al., 2020). A graphical schematisation of the original immunoassay (strategy A) and the four simplified immunoassays proposed (strategies B-E) is shown in Fig. 1.

The 3G8 or 10C9 mAb-MB conjugates, used in all strategies, were prepared as previously described (Leonardo et al., 2020). Briefly, to produce 1 mL of mAb-MB conjugate, 100 µL of MBs was transferred to a tube and washed twice with 1 mL of MES (25 mM MES buffer, pH 5.0). For the washing steps, the tube was placed on a magnetic separation stand to remove supernatants. The MBs were subsequently incubated with 1 mL of EDC and NHS at 25 mg/mL each in MES for 30 min. Then, after washing twice with MES, 1 mL of 3G8 or 10C9 mAb at 130 µg/mL in MES was added to the activated MBs and incubated for 1 h. Finally, the mAb-MB conjugates were washed three times with PBST (0.1 M phosphate buffered saline, 0.05 % (v/v) Tween-20, pH 7.2) and resuspended in 1 mL of the same buffer.

Once mAb-MB conjugates were prepared, the sandwich immunoassay was constructed following different simplified strategies, whose optimised protocols are described below.

Strategy A is a four-step sandwich immunoassay where each reagent is incubated in an independent and subsequent step (Leonardo et al., 2020). First, 35 µL of each conjugate (3G8-MB and 10C9-MB) were mixed in a tube and placed on a magnetic separation stand for supernatant removal. Then, 35 µL of toxin or fish extract, previously evaporated and reconstituted with PBST, was added and incubated for 30 min. After three washing steps, a 30-min blocking step with 35 µL of PBST-BSA (1 % BSA (w/v)) was performed. Then, the MBs were washed three times and, 35 µL of biotinylated 8H4 mAb at 2 µg/mL in PBST-BSA was added and incubated for 30 min. After three washing steps, 35 µL of polyHRP-streptavidin at 0.5 µg/mL in PBST-BSA was added and incubated for 30 min. Finally, the immunocomplexes were washed three

Fig. 1. Graphical schematisation of the steps required for immunoassay construction with the original strategy (strategy A) and the four simplified strategies (strategy B-E) proposed in this work (a 60-min incubation time was also tested in the optimisation of strategy E). All strategies require a final 10-min incubation for colour development and signal measurement, not shown in the scheme.

times and resuspended in 35 µL of the same buffer. For the optimisation study, polyHRP-streptavidin at 2 µg/mL was also tested.

Strategy B is a two-step sandwich immunoassay where the conjugates and the biotinylated 8H4 mAb are firstly incubated with the sample, while the polyHRP-streptavidin is added in a subsequent incubation step. First, 35 µL of each conjugate (3G8-MB and 10C9-MB) were mixed in a tube and placed on a magnetic separation stand for supernatant removal. Then, 35 µL of toxin, previously evaporated and reconstituted with a biotinylated 8H4 mAb solution at 2 µg/mL in PBST-

BSA, was added and incubated for 30 min. After three washing steps, 35 µL of polyHRP-streptavidin at 2 µg/mL in PBST-BSA was added and incubated for 30 min. Finally, the immunocomplexes were washed three times and resuspended with 35 µL of the same buffer. For the optimisation study, polyHRP-streptavidin at 0.5 µg/mL was also tested.

Strategy C is a two-step sandwich immunoassay where the conjugates are firstly exposed to the sample and subsequently incubated with a previously prepared solution of the biotinylated 8H4 mAb with the polyHRP-streptavidin (8H4-polyHRP). To prepare 1 mL of 8H4-

polyHRP, 500 μL of biotinylated 8H4 mAb at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in PBST and 500 μL of polyHRP-streptavidin at 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in PBST were mixed in a tube and incubated for 30 min. The 8H4-polyHRP was freshly prepared every day. For the assay, 35 μL of each conjugate (3G8-MB and 10C9-MB) were mixed in a tube and placed on a magnetic separation stand for supernatant removal. Then, 35 μL of toxin, previously evaporated and reconstituted in PBST-BSA, was added and incubated for 30 min. After three washing steps, 35 μL of the 8H4-polyHRP solution was added and incubated for 30 min. Finally, the immunocomplexes were washed three times and resuspended in 35 μL of the same buffer. For the optimisation study, polyHRP-streptavidin at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was also tested.

Strategy D is a two-step sandwich immunoassay where the sample, the biotinylated 8H4 mAb and the polyHRP-streptavidin are incubated together, and then exposed to the conjugates in a subsequent incubation step. Initially, 40 μL of toxin was evaporated and reconstituted with PBST-BSA containing biotinylated 8H4 mAb at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and polyHRP-streptavidin at 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$. The mixture was incubated for 30 min (mixture 1). In parallel, 35 μL of each conjugate (3G8-MB and 10C9-MB) were mixed in a tube and placed on a magnetic separation stand for supernatant removal (mixture 2). Then, 35 μL of the mixture 1 were added to the mixture 2 and incubated for 30 min. Finally, the immunocomplexes were washed three times and resuspended in 35 μL of the same buffer. For the optimisation study, polyHRP-streptavidin at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was also tested.

Strategy E is a single-step sandwich immunoassay where all components are simultaneously incubated with the sample. Initially, 35 μL of each conjugate (3G8-MB and 10C9-MB) were mixed in a tube and placed on a magnetic separation stand for supernatant removal. Then, 30 μL of toxin or fish extract, previously evaporated and reconstituted with PBST-BSA, and 5 μL of a mixture of biotinylated 8H4 mAb at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ and polyHRP-streptavidin at 2 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ in PBST-BSA were added and incubated for 30 min. Finally, the immunocomplexes were washed three times with PBST and resuspended in 35 μL of the same buffer. For the optimisation study, polyHRP-streptavidin at 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, biotinylated 8H4 mAb at 1 and 0.5 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$, and 60 min incubation time were also tested.

For all strategies, colour development and signal measurement were performed as follows: 10 μL of immunocomplexes (in triplicate) were transferred to a new tube and placed on a magnetic separation stand for supernatant removal. Then, 125 μL of TMB solution was added and incubated for 10 min. The tube was placed on a magnetic separation stand and 100 μL of solution was taken for absorbance measurement at 620 nm.

Full dose-response curves were constructed at different concentrations of CTX1B ranging from 1000 to 0.48 pg/mL of CTX1B. Fishes were analysed at different flesh equiv. concentrations ranging from 2500 to 39 mg/mL , depending on the specimen. All incubation steps were performed at room temperature and with slow tilt rotation. All washing steps were performed with PBST.

2.5. Cell-based assay (CBA)

Neuro-2a cells were maintained in RPMI-1640 media supplemented with 10 % (v/v) FBS, 1 % (v/v) penicillin-streptomycin, and 1 % (v/v) sodium pyruvate at 37 °C in a 5 % CO₂ humid atmosphere. The Neuro-2a CBA was performed as previously described (Diogène et al., 2017). Initially, cells were trypsinised and seeded in a 96-well microplate at 35,000 cells/well with 200 μL of culture media containing 5 % (v/v) FBS. Cells were then incubated for 24 h at 37 °C in a 5 % CO₂ humid atmosphere. Prior to extract exposure, some cells were pretreated with 20 μL of an ouabain (O) and veratridine (V) mixture in PBS at 0.1 and 0.01 mM, respectively. Then, fish extracts were dried, reconstituted in culture media, ½ serially diluted, and 10 μL of each dilution was added into the wells with and without O/V pretreatment. After a 24-h incubation at 37 °C in a 5 % CO₂ humid atmosphere, cell viability was measured using the MTT assay (Kogure et al., 1988). Full dose-response curves were

constructed using different concentrations of CTX1B ranging from 12.5 to 0.10 pg/mL . Fishes were analysed at different flesh equiv. concentrations ranging from 10 to 0.04 mg/mL , depending on the specimen. Measurements were performed in triplicate.

2.6. Statistical analysis

All data were processed using the SigmaPlot 12.0 software (Systat Software, San Jose, CA, USA), which was used for statistical analysis. Paired t-tests, applying a 95 % confidence level, were performed to identify the differences between the average of two groups whose data followed a normal distribution. Normality was checked using the Shapiro-Wilk test with a 95 % of confidence level.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Evaluation of the stability of the mAb-MB conjugates

The use of MBs as physical supports for the immobilisation of antibodies in immunoassays had been explored in the development of the original sandwich immunoassay (strategy A) because of the advantages they can entail for the analysis of specific targets at trace concentrations in complex fish extracts (Leonardo et al., 2020). The use of MBs increases the surface-to-volume ratio regarding the immobilisation of biorecognition molecules, improves the assay kinetics, increases the efficiency of washing steps, and reduces the assay interferences due to matrix effects (Gaiani et al., 2019). For example, the limit of detection (LOD) of a competitive immunoassay for the detection of tetrodotoxins (TTXs) in shellfish was reduced by more than one order of magnitude when using MBs (Campàs et al., 2020) instead of microtiter plates (Reverté et al., 2018) as immobilisation supports. Taking under consideration the advantages the use of MBs offers, the mAb-MB conjugates used in the original assay (strategy A) were also used for the simplified strategies (strategies B-E). Additionally, in this work, the possibility to prepare a stock of mAb-MB conjugates ready to use, avoiding the synthesis that same day and, therefore, reducing the time required for analysis, was evaluated.

In order to evaluate the stability of the mAb-MBs conjugates under different storage temperatures, large batches of 3G8-MB and 10C9-MB conjugates were produced, mixed at 1:1 ratio and kept at 4 °C or -20 °C. The response obtained when exposing the conjugates to 100 pg/mL of CTX1B (specific signal) was measured every month using the strategy A protocol. The specific signals obtained from the months two to twelve were not statistically different to that obtained at the beginning of the experiment (month zero) ($P = 0.359$) (Supplementary section, Figure S1). This result indicated that the mAb-MB conjugates are stable for, at least, 12 months when stored both at 4 °C and -20 °C, which is beneficial not only because it allows a reduction of the analysis time by 90 min, but also because it improves the reproducibility as the same batch of mAb-MB conjugates can be used for different assay runs.

3.2. Removal of the blocking step

Blocking steps may be essential in some immunoassays to decrease the non-specific adsorptions and to improve the signal-to-noise ratio, but they may not be strictly necessary if immunoassay incubations are performed in the presence of a blocking agent, such as BSA, which could coat the surface of the mAb-MB conjugates meanwhile the immunoassay architecture is being constructed (Campàs et al., 2020). To test if the blocking step in the original strategy was necessary, the response with and without this blocking step was assessed using the strategy A protocol and the protocol without the blocking step but adding BSA in all incubation steps (Supplementary section, Figure S2). The specific signal (100 pg/mL of CTX1B) obtained without the blocking step was not statistically different ($P = 0.786$) from that obtained when the blocking step was included. Given that the non-specific signal was only marginally

higher in the absence of the blocking step and a good signal-to-noise ratio was maintained, the blocking step with BSA was removed in the subsequent simplified strategies, reducing the time required for analysis by 30 min more.

3.3. Optimisation of the simplified strategies

In the original sandwich immunoassay (strategy A), reagents are added in sequential incubations separated by washing steps (Leonardo et al., 2020). However, in the simplified immunoassays (strategies B-E), two or more immunoreagents are combined with the aim of reducing the number of incubation steps and the time required for analysis, and therefore simplifying the whole assay process. However, the combination of reagents can affect the detection capabilities of the immunoassay. For this reason, the specific signals towards CTX1B obtained with the four proposed simplified strategies (strategies B-E) were measured to identify issues related to undesired steric impediments and/or cross-reactivities potentially affecting the detection of CTXs and decreasing the absorbance values.

In an initial screening, the concentrations of biotinylated 8H4 mAb (2 µg/mL) and polyHRP-streptavidin (0.5 µg/mL) used in the original assay protocol (strategy A) were applied to the simplified assays (strategies B-E) (Fig. 2, grey bars). The signal obtained with strategy B after exposing the conjugates to 100 pg/mL of CTX1B was 32 % higher than the one obtained with strategy A. The main difference between the two protocols is that, in strategy A, the toxin interacts firstly with the immobilised capture antibody (3G8 or 10C9) and subsequently, in an independent incubation step, with the reporter antibody (8H4), whereas in strategy B, the toxin interacts with both antibodies at the same time. Based on the high absorbance values obtained with strategy B, it is safe to say that the simultaneous interaction of both antibodies with the toxin enhances the detection capability of the assay, providing higher signals for a given CTX1B concentration. On the contrary, the signals obtained with strategy C, D and E were 64–70 % lower, indicating that, under the tested conditions, their detection capabilities are worse. In a

conventional sequential sandwich immunoassay (like in strategy A), reagents are added in excess to maximise the efficiency of the reaction, and after incubation this excess is eliminated through washing steps. However, when different reagents are combined (like in the simplified strategies), a shift in the reaction equilibrium may occur if at least one of the reagents is in excess or even in insufficient amount (Amarasiri-Fernando and Wilson, 1992). This could be the case for strategy C, D and E, which may require an optimisation of the biotinylated 8H4 mAb and/or the polyHRP-streptavidin concentrations to ensure that none of the reagents is affecting the reaction. The concentration of mAb-MB conjugates could also be included in this optimisation process, but it was decided to be maintained for budgetary reasons.

It is important to highlight that the two protocols with higher signals (strategies A and B) were the only ones where the polyHRP-streptavidin was added in an independent incubation step. This result suggested that the polyHRP-streptavidin concentration could be a limiting factor when combined with other reagents (like in strategies C, D and E) but not when added alone (like in strategies A and B). To verify this issue, a higher polyHRP-streptavidin concentration (2 µg/mL) was tested (Fig. 2, white bars). The specific signals obtained with strategies A and B after exposing the mAb-MB conjugates to 100 pg/mL of CTX1B increased by 23 and 36 %, respectively. The strategies C and D did not show any improvement in the specific signal, whereas strategy E signal increased by 161 %. The improvement of the strategy E performance when tested at a higher polyHRP-streptavidin concentration indicated that this component certainly was a limiting factor in the previous experiment. On the contrary, the lack of improvement observed for strategies C and D indicated that other factors, different from the polyHRP-streptavidin concentration, might be affecting the performance of the assay. The incubation of the antibodies with the toxin in the strategies C and D is performed in separated incubation steps, where big molecular complexes (8H4-polyHRP for strategy C and CTX-8H4-polyHRP for strategy D) need to acquire an appropriate orientation. Considering the size of those molecular complexes, steric impediments may be hampering the acquisition of this orientation and, therefore, the construction of the

Fig. 2. Signals obtained with the original immunoassay (strategy A) and the four simplified approaches (strategy B-E) under different concentrations of polyHRP-streptavidin and a fixed concentration of biotinylated 8H4 monoclonal antibody (mAb) (2 µg/mL). Bars represent the average ± the standard deviation of the absorbance values at 620 nm (n = 3).

immunoassay architecture, as observed in other works (Reverté et al., 2013). Based on these results, strategies C and D were discarded.

Out of the two remaining simplified strategies (strategies B and E), strategy E is more interesting than strategy B in terms of simplicity and analysis time because it is a single-step immunoassay that allows the construction of the immunoassay in only 30 min, while strategy B is a two-step that requires 60 min. However, the specific signals obtained with strategy B were always higher than the ones obtained with strategy E. With the aim of optimising the detection capabilities of strategy E, different concentration ratios of biotinylated 8H4 mAb and polyHRP-streptavidin were tested (Supplementary section, Figure S3). The results showed that increasing concentrations of polyHRP-streptavidin or biotinylated 8H4 mAb did not always increase the specific signal. For example, at the highest concentrations of both components, the signal was not the highest. This was likely due to an imbalance in the concentrations of the immunoassay components, which resulted in steric impediments. The maximal signal was obtained with a concentration of 2 µg/mL for biotinylated 8H4 mAb and 2 µg/mL for polyHRP-streptavidin, which were established as the optimal conditions for strategy E.

Since the specific signals obtained with strategy E still did not reach the values obtained with strategy B, higher incubation times were tested. Considering that the main objective of this work is to provide a rapid immunoassay for the detection of Pacific CTXs in fish, incubation times higher than 60 min were not considered. The specific and non-specific signals obtained with the strategy E protocol at incubation times ranging from 5 to 60 min were recorded (Supplementary section, Figure S4), obtaining higher specific signals at longer incubation times and not noticing any change in the non-specific signals. The highest signal with the strategy E protocol was obtained when using a 60-min incubation time, achieving a value similar to the one obtained with strategy B of the initial screening experiment with a concentration of 2

µg/mL of biotinylated 8H4 mAb and 0.5 µg/mL of polyHRP-streptavidin. Although a 60-min incubation could improve the detection capabilities of strategy E, it would substantially increase the assay time. At this juncture, it becomes evident that a compromise between sensitivity and assay time needs to be considered. It is necessary to guarantee the detection of Pacific CTXs with an appropriate sensitivity in the shortest analysis time possible. Therefore, the analytical performance of the simplified strategies, including in the presence of a fish matrix, needs to be carefully assessed.

3.4. Analytical parameters of strategies B and E

To evaluate the different analytical parameters from strategies B and E (the latter using 30-min and 60-min incubation time), full dose-response curves for CTX1B were constructed and compared with the one obtained with the original immunoassay (strategy A) (Fig. 3).

All data were blank-subtracted and fitted to a sigmoidal logistic four-parameter equation, which was used to calculate the LOD, the limit of quantification (LOQ) and the median effective concentration (EC₅₀) for each strategy (Table 2). The LODs and LOQs were calculated using 3 and

Table 2

Limit of detection (LOD), limit of quantification (LOQ) and median effective concentration (EC₅₀) from strategy A, B and E (the latter using 30-min and 60-min incubation time). Values represent the average ± the standard deviation, expressed in pg CTX1B/mL (n = 12).

Strategy	LOD	LOQ	EC ₅₀
A	7 ± 1	29 ± 2	126 ± 5
B	6 ± 2	20 ± 2	89 ± 4
E (30-min)	7 ± 3	27 ± 2	128 ± 5
E (60-min)	6 ± 1	14 ± 1	79 ± 4

Fig. 3. Dose-response curves for CTX1B constructed with the original immunoassay (strategy A) and two simplified strategies (strategies B and E, the latter using 30-min and 60-min incubation time). Each point represents the average ± the standard deviation of the absorbance values at 620 nm (n = 3).

10 times, respectively, the standard deviation of the blank (non-specific signal). The EC_{50} was defined as the concentration of CTX1B required for obtaining a signal corresponding to 50 % of the maximal response of the assay.

There are no statistical differences between the original immunoassay (strategy A) and the 30-min strategy E when comparing LODs ($P = 0.640$), LOQs ($P = 0.284$) or EC_{50} values ($P = 0.508$). With regard to the 60-min strategy E, although the LOD was not statistically different from the one obtained with strategy A ($P = 0.128$), the LOQ and EC_{50} values were certainly lower ($P < 0.05$). The strategy B showed the same LOD as strategy A ($P = 0.126$), but significantly lower LOQ and EC_{50} values ($P < 0.05$). However, since the LOQ and EC_{50} values from 60-min strategy E were significantly lower than those obtained with strategy B ($P < 0.05$) and considering that, although the assay time is the same, the first is a single-step assay whereas the second is a two-step assay, the strategy B was discarded.

Although when using CTX standard solutions in buffer, the 60-min configuration was more sensitive than the 30-min one, it is crucial to assess the detection capabilities of these strategies in the presence of fish matrix. Therefore, an experiment was conducted using an extract of a pool of *V. louti* specimens that tested negative in both the Neuro-2a CBA assay and the original immunoassay (strategy A), which was spiked with CTX1B standard solution at a level of 0.01 μg CTX1B equiv./kg of fish flesh (which is the safety guidance level proposed by the FDA (Chinain et al., 2021)). The extract was $\frac{1}{2}$ serially diluted and analysed using the original immunoassay strategy (strategy A) and the two remaining simplified strategies (strategy E with 30-min and 60-min incubation times). It is important to emphasize that a negative result from the immunoassay (strategy A) prior to spiking indicates absence of CTX congeners from the CTX1B or CTX3C series in the sample. Additionally, a negative result from the Neuro-2a CBA assay before spiking suggests absence of compounds with CTX-like activity. Therefore, any signal detected after spiking must be attributed solely to the spiked CTX1B and not to other compounds previously present in the sample. As it can be observed in Fig. 4, the strategy A and E using a 30-min incubation time showed recoveries in the range of 57–66 % when analysed at 2500 mg

fish equiv./mL. In contrast, the strategy E using a 60-min incubation time showed a recovery of only 36 %. Recovery values lower than 100 % are indicative of matrix effects, which are hindering the recognition of CTXs by the antibodies and/or the interaction between the other components in the immunoassay architecture. At 1250 mg fish equiv./mL, the recoveries from strategies A and E using a 30-min incubation time increased up to 97 and 102 %, respectively. However, with regard to the 60-min incubation time, the matrix effects were persistent at 1250 and 625 mg fish equiv./mL, showing recoveries of only 55 and 63 %, respectively. Based on these results, it is safe to say that strategy E using a 60-min incubation time is more prone to matrix effects than when using a 30-min incubation time. For this reason, the strategy E using a 60-min incubation time was discarded.

Therefore, the strategy E using a 30-min incubation time was selected as the optimal simplified approach from this work. Using this strategy, the accuracy at 0.01 μg CTX1B equiv./kg was 102 % and 110 % when analysing the sample at 1250 and 625 mg/mL, respectively. The repeatability and intermediate precision were evaluated by performing multiple measurements on the same day and different days, respectively. The relative standard deviation (RSD) value for the measurements performed on the same day was 15 % ($N = 3$) at 1250 mg/mL and 15 % ($N = 3$) at 625 mg/mL, and for the measurements performed on different days was 17 % ($N = 3$) at 1250 mg/mL and 26 % ($N = 3$) at 625 mg/mL. Summarising, this strategy demonstrated the ability to accurately detect CTXs at the FDA safety guidance level, matching the performance of the original strategy (strategy A) but with only one step and in a shorter time assay, requiring only 30 min for the construction of the immunoassay architecture.

3.5. Analysis of naturally contaminated samples with the single-step strategy

The performance of strategy E using a 30-min incubation time with regard to the detection of Pacific CTXs in naturally contaminated samples was evaluated. In toxin monitoring programs, sample analysis is conducted at a single matrix concentration, with extracts being diluted

Fig. 4. Analysis of several dilutions of a *Variola louti* flesh extract spiked at the United States FDA safety guidance level of 0.01 μg CTX1B equiv./kg. The spiked level is indicated with a dotted line. Bars represent the average \pm the standard deviation, expressed in μg CTX1B equiv./kg ($n = 3$).

and reanalysed if toxin levels fall outside the calibration curve. Some Standard Operating Procedures define acceptable recovery percentages for method validation using reference materials (EURLMB, 2025a) or establish that each laboratory must assess matrix effects on their instrumentation and determine if correction is necessary, using reference material or spiked extracts (EURLMB, 2025b). However, matrix effects are likely to be highly variable among specimens. Thereby, a well-designed recovery experiment does not always guarantee a proper accuracy of the toxin contents in the fish. This work proposes the analysis of serial dilutions of a fish extract as an alternative to the use of recovery correction factors. While this strategy may not be ideal for a hypothetical monitoring programme due to the associated costs, it is useful in this work as it allows the accurate determination of the CTX contents and helps to better understand the impact of the fish matrix effects on the performance of the assay.

The CTX contents in two *V. louti* and two *Lutjanus bohar* flesh extracts were determined with the single-step assay (strategy E using a 30-min incubation time) at several matrix dilutions, and results were compared with those obtained with the original immunoassay (strategy A) (Fig. 5). The same samples were also analysed with a Neuro-2a CBA. The CBA calibration curve and the analysis of one sample as an example are shown in Supplementary section, Figure S5. The CTX contents determined with the three analytical techniques are summarised in Table 3.

Table 3

CTX contents in the flesh extracts from two different *Variola louti* and *Lutjanus bohar* specimens determined with the original immunoassay (strategy A), the single-step immunoassay (strategy E) and a Neuro-2a cell-based assay (CBA). Values are expressed in μg CTX1B equiv./kg ($n = 3$).

Sample		Strategy A	Strategy E	CBA
<i>Variola louti</i>	04/DIV/03	0.35	0.31	0.35
	15/41	0.16	0.10	2.08
<i>Lutjanus bohar</i>	03/DIV/21	0.06	0.09	0.67
	02/DIV/38	0.93	0.93	1.13

Our sandwich immunoassay provided the highest absorbance values at the highest fish extract concentrations, in this case at 2500 mg/mL (data not shown). However, once these signals were translated into CTX contents expressed in μg of CTX1B equiv./kg fish, the highest concentrations of the sample resulted in the lowest CTX contents (Fig. 5). This is due to the matrix effects, which hinder the detection of CTXs at high fish matrix concentrations, as observed in other works (Leonardo et al., 2020). The impact of the fish matrix on the CTX contents decreases with the dilution of samples, reaching a stabilisation at the lowest fish extract concentrations. This effect is easily observed for sample 04/DIV/03. However, regarding the samples 15/41, 03/DIV/21 and 02/DIV/38, the stabilisation of the CTX contents is not so evident since it was not possible to dilute the sample further without losing the signal. Although

Fig. 5. Analysis of flesh extracts corresponding to two *Variola louti* and two *Lutjanus bohar* specimens at different fish matrix concentrations with the original immunoassay (strategy A) and the single-step assay (strategy E using a 30-min incubation time). Bars represent the average \pm standard deviation, expressed in μg of CTX1B equiv./kg fish ($n = 3$).

we cannot rule out the fact that for these samples the CTX quantifications can still be influenced by some matrix compounds, it is evident that this fact is not a consequence of the single-step assay performance (strategy E), as the same trend was observed with the original immunoassay (strategy A). In fact, the CTX contents at all dilutions are quite similar in both immunoassay strategies, regardless the sample. This result indicates that although the strategy E combines MBs, antibodies, enzyme labels, CTXs and fish matrix compounds all together, is not more prone to matrix effects, being as affective as the original immunoassay (strategy A) in the analysis of naturally contaminated samples.

It is important to note that all the samples from this study tested positive for CTXs using different analytical techniques (strategy A, strategy E and Neuro-2a CBA), with CTX contents exceeding the FDA safety guidance level of 0.01 µg CTX1B equiv./kg (Chinain et al., 2021). However, there were some discrepancies among techniques regarding the CTX contents. While the CTX contents were similar between immunoassay configurations (strategy A or E), in some samples they were lower than those obtained with Neuro-2a CBA, certainly due to the different detection principles (Reverté et al., 2023). The CBA is a toxicological approach that detects CTXs based on their activity on VGSCs, whereas the immunoassay is a structural recognition approach whose detection is based on the affinity of antibodies against CTXs. In front of a sample with a multi-CTX profile, the CBA may be detecting different CTX congeners based on their toxicity on cells. However, the immunoassays only detect those CTX congeners able to cross-react with the antibodies, i.e. Pacific CTXs from the CTX1B and CTX3C series. This fact could explain the differences observed for samples 15/41, 03/DIV/21 and 02/DIV/38. Regarding sample 04/DIV/03, we could hypothesise that only Pacific CTXs from the CTX1B and CTX3C series are present. At this point it is important to highlight that data on the multi-CTX profile of the samples from LC-MS/MS analysis would have been interesting to better understand the differences between techniques. Nevertheless, the comparison between the simplified strategy and the original one is enough to demonstrate the feasibility of the new approach.

Sample 15/41 was the remains of a cooked fish involved in a CP case, which had been collected for CTX confirmation. This fish was consumed by 7 people, 6 of them presenting characteristic ciguatera symptoms (paraesthesia, superficial dysesthesia, headache, myalgia, diarrhoea, reversal of the hot and cold sensation, asthenia and pruritus). Besides the biological and environmental factors influencing the multi-CTX profile of a fish, the method of preparation, particularly cooking, may also play a significant role in the molecular structures and toxicity of CTXs (Abraham et al., 2012). Finally, it is essential to highlight the need for structural elucidation of all CTX congeners present in nature, particularly those from the Indian Ocean, which remain poorly characterised. This knowledge is crucial to produce highly specific antibodies against different CTX congeners, which could be integrated into the current analytical technology, such as the one proposed in this work, to provide useful surveillance tools for CP prevention and human health protection.

4. Conclusions

In this work, four simplified strategies of a MB-based sandwich immunoassay were evaluated with the aim of providing a rapid and highly sensitive bioanalytical tool for the detection of Pacific CTXs in fish samples. In these strategies, immunoassay reagents were combined to reduce the number of incubation and washing steps, thereby shortening the analysis time and the complexity of the assay (making it more user-friendly). Not all the strategies were suitable for the detection of CTXs, since the combination of immunoassay reagents may lead to steric impediments hindering the construction of the sandwich immunoassay architecture. After a proper optimisation of the concentration of immunoassay reagents and incubation time, the single-step immunoassay, where the capture and reporter mAbs are incubated together with the toxin, as well as with the enzyme label, provided absorbance values comparable to the ones obtained with the original strategy. This

strategy, which takes only 40 min (30 min for the incubation and 10 min for the reading) and drastically reduces the number of washing steps, was proven to be able to detect as low as 0.01 µg CTX1B equiv./kg, which is the FDA safety guidance level for this toxin family, and to be applicable to the analysis of naturally contaminated samples. This single-step MB-based sandwich immunoassay showed to be a rapid and highly sensitive bioanalytical tool with great potential to be applied in research and monitoring programs to protect consumers from CP.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Jaume Reverté: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Shivangi Shukla:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Takeshi Tsumuraya:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Masahiro Hiram:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Jean Turquet:** Writing – review & editing, Resources, Funding acquisition. **Jorge Diogène:** Writing – review & editing. **Mónica Campàs:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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